

The Solubility and Micellar Behaviour of dl-tris(en) Cobalt(III) Soaps in Various Solvents

WAHID U. MALIK, AJAY K. JAIN*, V. K. VELU and A. K. CHHIBBAR

Department of Chemistry, University of Roorkee, Roorkee-247 667

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A new series of cobalt complex soaps, *vis.* dl-tris(en) cobalt(III) myristate, palmitate and stearate have been synthesised and their solubility behaviour in various solvents was investigated using ^{59}Co as tracer. The results indicate that these cobalt complex soaps are about 10-50 times more soluble than ordinary cobalt soaps. The higher solubility has been explained on the basis of weaker polar bonding. Further, the solubility has been found to increase as the length of the hydrocarbon chain in the soap decreases. The variation in the solubility of these soaps with temperature has been used to determine their critical micelle concentration and Krafft point.

PLIPEL¹, while reviewing the properties of organic solutions of heavy metal soaps, has pointed out that they are soluble in a wide variety of organic solvents and yield gels, colloidal dispersions and liquids. However, our investigations during the last fifteen years using highly sensitive radiotracer technique have shown that cobalt^{2,3}, cadmium⁴, silver⁵ and chromium⁶ soaps are only sparingly soluble in most of the organic solvents at room temperature. The low solubility of metal soaps adversely affect their utility in industry. For example, it is reported that difficulties are encountered in making appropriate and specific lubricating preparations⁶ due to the low solubility of the metal soaps. It is thus expected that these soaps can be more profitably used if their solubility can be enhanced. We have, therefore, started preparing modified metal soaps by interacting metal complex cations with ionic surfactants and have found that cobalt hexammine soaps^{7,8} are much more soluble than cobalt soaps. This increase in solubility has been assigned to large size⁷ of cobalt hexammine cation. In order to further support this conclusion, we have synthesised dl-tris(en) cobalt(III) soaps and report in the present communication on their solubility and micellization behaviour in large number of pure solvents.

isotopic exchange. This solution was then used for the preparation of labelled dl-tris(en) cobalt(III) chloride by the reported method⁹.

Preparation of labelled dl-tris(en) cobalt(III) soaps: Labelled dl-tris(en) cobalt(III) myristate, palmitate and stearate were prepared by interacting aqueous solution of the corresponding sodium soaps (0.01 M) with an aqueous solution of labelled dl-tris(en) Co^{III} chloride (0.02 M). The complex was added in slight excess. The precipitated soaps were filtered, washed with double-distilled water and alcohol and then dried in a vacuum desiccator. The unlabelled cobalt complex soaps were similarly prepared and the formulae were assigned on the basis of elemental analysis (Table 1).

Soaps	TABLE-1 Analysis % ; Found/(Calcd.)		
	O	H	N
dl-tris(en) Co ^{III} stearate Co(en) ₃ (C ₁₇ H ₃₅ COO) ₃	66.43 (66.14)	11.76 (11.93)	7.58 (7.91)
dl-tris(en) Co ^{III} palmitate Co(en) ₃ (C ₁₅ H ₃₁ COO) ₃	64.75 (64.50)	12.03 (11.79)	8.10 (8.36)
dl-tris(en) Co ^{III} myristate Co(en) ₃ (C ₁₃ H ₂₇ COO) ₃	62.92 (62.57)	11.65 (11.49)	9.40 (9.12)

Experimental

Sodium myristate, palmitate and stearate (reagent grade BDH) were used after purification by extraction using acetone and then recrystallisation from alcohol. All other reagents were of AR grade and solvents purified by standard methods. The radiotracer ^{59}Co was obtained as cobalt chloride in HCl solution from B.A.R.C., Bombay.

Preparation of labelled dl-tris(en) cobalt(III) chloride: A small amount of ^{59}Co activity was added to an aqueous solution of 2.4 g inactive cobalt chloride in 10 ml water and the resulting mixture was warmed up to bring about complete

Solubility measurements: Each saturated solution was prepared by the agitation of an excess of labelled cobalt complex soap in a pyrex stoppered conical flask about half-full of solvent. Attainment of solubility equilibria was indicated by the constancy of the counting rate (activity) on successive measurements with supernatant solution. Aliquots were filtered through Whatman 42 paper and their activity determined on a gamma ray scintillation spectrometer. Specific activity of each cobalt complex soap was determined by measuring the activity of the standard solution of the soap in methanol. All activity measurements were made

TABLE 2—SOLUBILITY VALUES OF DL-TRIS(en) COBALT(III) SOAPS AT 30°

Solvent	dl-tris(en)	dl-tris(en)	dl-tris(en)	Hexammine	Co ^{II} stearate** × 10 ⁻⁵ M
	Co ^{III} myristate × 10 ⁻⁵ M	Co ^{III} palmitate × 10 ⁻⁵ M	Co ^{III} stearate × 10 ⁻⁵ M	Co ^{III} stearate* × 10 ⁻⁵ M	
Benzene	21.9	15.4	11.9	7.3	0.79
Toluene	41.0	26.7	17.9	8.1	0.34
m-Xylene	49.0	36.0	28.2	12.0	1.07
Nitrobenzene	18.5	15.8	11.5	7.0	0.83
Chlorobenzene	24.3	19.2	17.6	10.1	0.33
Ethyl methyl ketone	16.5	13.7	11.7	6.1	1.13
Water	6.0	6.0	5.2	4.8	0.42
Dioxan	25.0	21.5	18.2	15.7	1.08
Acetone	12.3	8.8	7.3	5.8	0.28

* Ref. 7. ** Ref. 3.

TABLE 3—C.S.T. AND CMC VALUES OF DL-TRIS(en) COBALT(III) SOAPS IN VARIOUS SOLVENTS

Solvent	Stearate		Palmitate		Myristate	
	C.S.T. °C	cmc × 10 ⁴ M	C.S.T. °C	cmc × 10 ⁴ M	C.S.T. °C	cmc × 10 ⁴ M
Benzene	51.5	36.0	47.5	44.0	44.0	61.0
Toluene	52.5	28.5	48.0	37.0	45.0	53.0
m-Xylene	58.0	13.0	50.0	59.0	46.0	77.0
Nitrobenzene	68.0	16.0	64.5	24.5	61.0	33.0
Chlorobenzene	63.0	18.5	59.0	22.0	57.0	34.0

under the same geometrical conditions and appropriate corrections were made for coincidence loss and the decay of the isotope.

Results and Discussion

Solubility behaviour: The solubility values of dl-tris(en) Co^{III} soaps (together with cobalt stearate⁸ and hexammine cobalt stearate⁷ for the purpose of comparison) are given in Table 2. It is seen that these cobalt complex soaps are not highly soluble in both the polar and non-polar solvents. However, they are about 10-50 times more soluble than the ordinary cobalt soaps⁸. This difference appears due to varying extent of polar bonding in the soaps. In ordinary cobalt soaps, carboxylate group which is a moderately strong base¹⁰ interacts with cobalt(II) ion, a strong Lewis acid. Due to small size of Cu^{II} ion, strong polar bonding exists in the cobalt(II) soaps molecules leading to their low solubility both in polar and non-polar solvents¹⁰. On the other hand, the polar bonding becomes relatively weaker in dl-tris(en) Co^{III} soaps due to the larger size of the cation. This would naturally result in enhanced solubility of cobalt complex soaps in comparison to cobalt soaps in different solvents. This comparison suffers from a drawback that the hydrophobic content in cobalt(II) soap is different from that of dl-tris(en) cobalt(III) soaps which might be playing some role. However, the comparison of the solubility of dl-tris(en) Co^{III} stearate with that of hexammine Co^{III} stearate⁷, both having the same hydrophobic content shows that the former has higher solubility than the latter one. This is evidently due to the weaker polar bonding in view of large size of Co(en)₃³⁺ as compared to Co(NH₃)₆³⁺ ion. Thus our results indicate

that the metal soaps having large cationic part would have higher solubility due to weaker polar bonding.

Fig. 1. Effect of temperature on the solubility of dl-tris(en) cobalt(III) soaps in toluene.

Effect of carbon chain length: It is further evident from Table 2 that the solubility of cobalt complex soaps is a function of carbon chain length and increases from stearate to myristate (molar volume decreasing). This observation is consistent with Hildebrand and Scott's regular solution theory^{11,12}, that the solubility of a solute should increase with decrease of molar volume.

Effect of temperature on solubility: The effect of temperature on the solubility of cobalt complex soaps in benzene, toluene, *m*-xylene, nitrobenzene and chlorobenzene has also been investigated and the results obtained are shown only for toluene in Fig. 1. Similar results were obtained in other solvents. It is seen from Fig. 1 that at low temperature the variation in the solubility is rather small but after a particular temperature, known as critical solution temperature (C.S.T.) or Krafft point, the solubility is enhanced enormously with increase in temperature. This type of behaviour is characteristic of micelle forming substances and is evidently due to low solubility of the soap monomer and high solubility of the micelles. Such solubility behaviour was observed for cadmium⁴, silver⁵, chromium⁶, cobalt⁸ and hexammine cobalt(III)⁷, lead¹³, zinc^{13,14} and copper¹⁵⁻¹⁷ soaps. The solubility at C.S.T. is taken as critical micelle concentration (cmc) of the soap. The C.S.T. and cmc values so determined are given in Table 3. It is interesting to note that the C.S.T. value decreases and cmc value increases as the carbon chain length is shortened, whereas the solubility increases from stearate to myristate (Table 2). It may, therefore, be concluded that higher the solubility of the soap, the lower is its C.S.T. and higher the cmc. This relationship between solubility and cmc is of course

expected because higher solubility indicates more affinity of the solvent for the soap monomer and thus leading to micellization at higher concentration.

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